

Influence of Organic Additives on the Flocculation of Sodium Cholate Stabilized O/W Emulsion

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Negatively charged toluene-in-water emulsion stabilized by sodium cholate was flocculated by cationic surfactants and the stability of the system discussed. Reversible flocculation occurring in secondary minimum region where the particles are trapped loosely was justified from electrophoretic and microscopic data. Some useful adsorption parameters for specific cationic binding were calculated at isoelectric point. The emulsions were flocculated at very small concentrations of cationic surfactants and were stabilized after the charge of the system was reversed. The flocculating values for surfactants were dependent upon their chain length. The influence of some alkanols on the emulsion stability was also examined.

THE surface activity of bile salts has long been recognized. These substances in aqueous solutions form micelles¹⁻³ and show solubilizing⁴ and emulsifying⁵ behaviour. The interaction of long chain quaternary ammonium ions with bile salts is a problem of biological importance. The mixed micelles and coacervates of mixtures of bile salts and cationic surfactants have been studied by Barry and Gray⁶. The influence of cationic surfactants and alkanols on the flocculation of sodium cholate stabilized emulsion has been examined and the findings are reported in this paper.

Experimental

Sodium cholate was obtained from Sigma Chemical Company. The cationic surfactants used were decyltrimethylammonium bromide (DeTAB), dodecylpyridinium chloride (DPC) and hexadecylpyridinium bromide (HPB) of BDH or Eastman Kodak make. These were purified till no minima in surface tension-concentration curves were observed.

Emulsions were prepared by dispersing 1% toluene in aqueous solution of sodium cholate (0.01%) in 0.01 M KCl. The mixture was homogenized through a stainless steel homogenizer which resulted in emulsions with an average particle size 2.10 micron diameter (determined from the microphotograph of the emulsions).

Haemocytometric studies in the presence of the cationic surfactants were made by counting the number of oil droplets in a fixed volume with the help of emulsion slides under a sensitive microscope at regular time intervals. Mobility measurements were made microelectrophoretically and the zeta potentials were calculated.

Theoretical :

To formulate quantitatively the DLVO theory, the total interaction energy, V , may be expressed as the sum of repulsive (V_R) and attractive (V_A) energies. The double layer repulsion in the present system which behaves as dilute hydrosol has been computed from an approximate equation due to Derjaguin and Kussakov⁷.

$$V_R = \frac{\epsilon a \psi_0^2}{2} \ln(1 + c^{-\kappa H}) \quad \dots (1)$$

where ψ_0 is the surface potential (identified as zeta potential), ϵ the dielectric constant, H the interparticle distance, κ the Debye-Huckel parameter and a the particle radius.

V_A is given by the following equations due to Schenkel and Kitchener⁸ :

$$V_A = -\frac{Aa}{12H} \left[\frac{\lambda}{\lambda + 3.54 \pi H} \right] \text{ for } H < 150 \text{ \AA} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$= -\frac{Aa}{\pi} \left[\frac{2.54 \lambda}{120 H^2} - \frac{\lambda^2}{1045 H^2} + \frac{\lambda^2}{5.62 \times 10^4 H^4} \right] \text{ for } H > 150 \text{ \AA} \quad \dots (2a)$$

where A is the van der Waals constant of the oil globules taken as equal to 2.8×10^{-18} erg for toluene dispersed in water, λ is the wave length of the London frequency (equal to 1000 Å).

At the isoelectric point, the adsorption constants are given by simple equations⁹

$$\frac{1}{C} = \frac{4\pi e v N_1 K_2}{\kappa \epsilon \psi_{0s}} - k_2 \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\left[\frac{d\psi_s}{d \ln C} \right]_{\psi_{0s}=0} = \left[\frac{\epsilon \psi_{0s} \kappa}{4\pi e v N_1} - 1 \right] \psi_{0s} \quad \dots (4)$$

where C is the concentration of the flocculation electrolyte at zero point of charge and v is the

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valency of the counter ions. N_1 is the slope of $\zeta - \log C$ curve.

The adsorption constants k_1 and k_2 can be calculated from the following equations¹⁰⁻¹¹ :

$$k_1 = N_1 k_2 e v \quad \dots (5)$$

and $k_2 = \frac{e^{-\Delta G/\kappa T}}{55.6} \quad \dots (6)$

The charge density of the Stern layer can be calculated with the help of the relation :

$$\sigma_s = \frac{k_1 C}{1 + k_2 C} \quad \dots (7)$$

ΔG , the electrochemical free energy of adsorption per molecule is given by the following equation¹² :

$$-\Delta G = kT (\ln k_2 + \ln 55.6) \quad \dots (8)$$

Results and Discussion

The fresh emulsion in absence of cationic surfactant had zeta potential -120.5 mV which decreased with the increasing concentration of cationic surfactants until the isoelectric point of the system is reached. On further addition of surfactant, an increase in zeta potential was observed. The variation in zeta potential with surfactant concentration is shown in Fig. 1 which is attributed to the specific adsorption of surface active cations into the Stern layer. Cationic surfactants were found better flocculants than simple polyvalent metal cations¹³ and their flocculating powers were dependant on the carbon chain length of surfactant, thus showing the order $HPB > DPC > DeTAB$.

The values of electrophoretic mobility, zeta potential, double layer thickness along with the calculated energy data are recorded in Table 1. The

Fig. 1. Plots of zeta potential against log molar concentration of various surfactants.

▲ -DeTAB, ○ -DPC, ■ -HPB.

interaction energies have also been plotted as a function of interparticle distance as represented in Fig. 2 for DeTAB. For other cationic surfactant concentrations, the energy maxima were $\gg 25$ kT which sometimes move to several thousand kT units. The presence of such high energy humps completely excludes the possibility of occurrence of primary minimum flocculation.

The emulsion system in absence or presence of cationic surfactants shows aggregation of individual particles on ageing, as examined microscopically. Initially, the emulsion contained 1.83×10^8 droplets (of size 2.10 micron diameter) per ml. The particle

TABLE 1—ELECTROPHORETIC DATA FOR SODIUM CHOLATE STABILIZED EMULSION IN PRESENCE OF CATIONIC SURFACTANTS

Dispersion medium : 0.01% sodium cholate in 0.01 M aqueous KCl
Dispersed phase : 1% toluene

Surfactant concentration mol l ⁻¹	Debye-Hückel parameter cm ⁻¹ × 10 ⁶	Electrophoretic mobility (micron/sec/volt/cm)	Zeta potential mV	V _{max} kT	Distance at V = 0 Å	Depth of the secondary minima kT
Zero	3.245	9.37	-120.55	8884	215	6.8
DeTAB						
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁶	3.245	6.08	-77.63	2953	182	7.9
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.245	5.45	-70.09	2321	168	8.2
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.253	4.78	-61.45	1670	160	9.3
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.261	3.93	-50.49	960	132	10.0
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	3.403	2.34	+30.10	170	104	20.7
5.0 × 10 ⁻³	3.975	3.92	+50.43	872	114	20.3
1.0 × 10 ⁻²	4.590	4.70	+67.51	1390	109	22.7
DPC						
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁶	3.245	4.60	-59.15	1510	163	8.5
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.245	3.53	-45.98	790	135	10.5
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.261	3.06	+39.42	470	115	14.5
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.326	4.47	+57.56	1390	143	10.2
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	3.403	5.33	+68.60	2160	155	9.5
HPB						
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁷	3.245	7.85	-100.91	5688	205	6.8
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶	3.245	6.83	-81.45	3380	187	8.0
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.253	4.11	+52.86	1160	150	10.3
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.261	4.94	+63.55	1820	158	9.3

TABLE 2—BINDING PARAMETERS FOR THE ADSORPTION OF CATIONIC SURFACTANTS ON TO SODIUM CHOLATE EMULSION GLOBULES

Cationic surfactant	Flocculation concentration mol l ⁻¹	Debye-Hückel parameter cm ⁻¹ × 10 ⁶	Number of binding sites available groups cm ⁻² × 10 ⁻¹³	ζ = 120.5 mV	
				K ₁	K ₂
DeTAB	5.00 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.326	70.28	22.88 × 10 ⁶	6.77 × 10 ³
DPC	3.55 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.251	60.18	32.93 × 10 ⁷	1.14 × 10 ⁴
HPB	7.94 × 10 ⁻⁶	3.246	51.44	15.85 × 10 ⁹	6.42 × 10 ⁴

Fig. 2. Plots of interaction energy vs interparticle distance with DeTAB.

- I. 5 × 10⁻⁶ M, II. 1 × 10⁻⁵ M, III. 5 × 10⁻⁵ M,
- IV. 1 × 10⁻⁴ M, V. 1 × 10⁻³ M, VI. 5 × 10⁻³ M,
- VII. 1 × 10⁻² M.

number at first decreases sharply and attains almost a constant value after 3-4 hr. The particle number also decreases with the increase in surfactant concentration. Such a change has been shown in Fig. 3 for emulsion in presence of DeTAB as a representative set of curves.

Since the system was found to be unstable, the flocculation has been assumed to occur in secondary minimum region. The elaborated secondary minima shown along side the energy diagram are sufficiently deep (ranging from 7-23 kT), when the particles were separated by a distance of about 100-200 Å.

The existence of secondary minima explains the possibility of reversible flocculation in the system which was further verified by gently shaking the flocculated emulsion when the aggregates were found redispersed. The adsorption constants k₁ and k₂, charge density in Stern layer, σ_s, number

Fig. 3. Plots of individual globules against time for the system flocculated by DeTAB.

- - 1 × 10⁻⁵ M, ▲ - 5 × 10⁻⁵ M, ■ - 1 × 10⁻⁴ M,
- - 1 × 10⁻³ M, × - 5 × 10⁻³ M, △ - 1 × 10⁻² M.

of binding sites available N₁ and free energy of adsorption ΔG have been calculated with the help of flocculating concentrations using the equations given in the theoretical part and the data obtained have been recorded in Tables 2 and 3. The adsorabilities of cations as denoted by k₂ values increase with increase in chain length of surfactant. This is also confirmed by the free energy data which were in the range 6-9 k cal mol⁻¹ and are high enough for adsorption.

TABLE 3—DATA FOR SODIUM CHOLATE STABILIZED EMULSION AT ISOELECTRIC POINT

Surfactant	Area/molecule Å ²	-ΔG	
		k cal mol ⁻¹	m coulomb mol ⁻¹
DeTAB	142.29	6.06	8.52
DPC	166.17	7.96	8.92
HPB	194.40	8.68	8.93

The ΔG values are reasonably high, as expected on the basis of the electrostatic adsorption of potential determining sites. An increase in ΔG values has been observed with the increase in chain length of the surface active agents. This implies that the charge reversal will take place at comparatively lower concentrations for detergents with longer chain lengths, because the larger the free energy of adsorption the smaller the number of cations

reaching the critical value of charge reversal concentration. Since the ΔG values are obtained at zero point of charge, these values must be close to the electrochemical free energy.

The influence of some alkanols on the electrophoretic mobility of the emulsions is depicted in Fig. 4 where a sharp decrease in electrophoretic mobility was found with an increase in alcohol concentrations. The calculations of zeta potential from mobility data were not made since the presence of alcohol in the emulsion significantly changes the viscosity and dielectric constant of the system.

Fig. 4. Plots of electrophoretic mobility against volume percent of alcohols.

○-Methyl alcohol, ×-Propyl alcohol, ●-Butyl alcohol.

The alcohols with dielectric constant lower than that of water ($\epsilon_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} = 33$, $\epsilon_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}} = 18.3$, $\epsilon_{\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH}} = 17$ and $\epsilon_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 78.5$) should increase the interionic attraction in the aqueous mixtures. The increase

in interionic attraction influences the existence of free polar heads (the hydrophilic end of the micelle which is so vital for emulsion stability) because it is likely to suppress the ionization of ionic emulsifiers. Further, likelihood of ion-pair formation is increased and the polar heads forming the micelle are likely to be surrounded by ions (from KCl added in the preparation of the emulsion and the ionizations of emulsifiers) of the opposite charge. These factors thus decrease the emulsifying activity of the emulsifier with increasing alcohol content in the aqueous mixtures and with the length of the carbon chain for a given percentage of different alcohols because dielectric constants are in the reverse order of the chain length.

The increase in interionic attraction should produce reduction in electrophoretic mobility and stability of the oil globules. In addition to this, as the concentration of an alcohol is increased, its adsorption at the surface of the oil globules increases; the adsorption being greater with the longer carbon chain in the alcohol molecule. With increase in adsorption of an alcohol, the number of the molecules of the emulsifier squeezed out of the surface of the oil globules increases and so the electrophoretic mobility is lowered further.

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